

VARIATION OF THE DISSOCIATION CONSTANT OF A WEAK ACID BY SOLUBILITY METHOD

By A. P. SHITOOT AND W. V. BHAGWAT

Variation of the dissociation constant of weak acids by solubility method has been investigated. The results are in accordance with the explanation given in previous papers by Bhagwat and co-workers.

It is observed by Bhagwat and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 807) and Bhagwat and Doosaj (*ibid.*, 1933, 10, 477) that the dissociation constant of weak acids determined by solubility method varies with the concentration of the sodium or potassium salt taken for this purpose. The work is extended in this paper.

TABLE I

Dissociation constant of glycollic acid.

- (i) With benzoic acid at 25°6'. K_1 of benzoic acid at 30° = 6.4×10^{-5} . $a = 0.02864$.
 (ii) With salicylic acid at 24°4'. K_1 of salicylic acid at 30° = 1.6×10^{-5} . $a = 0.01545$.

c .	b .	$K_2 = K_1.a.(c-b+a)/(b-a)^2$.	c .	b .	$K_2 = K_1.a.(c-b+a)/(b-a)^2$.
0.00514	0.03114	7.7×10^{-4}	0.00964	0.02341	6.5×10^{-4}
0.01456	0.03454	4.5	0.02892	0.03682	4.1
0.02892	0.04023	2.3	0.03856	0.04136	4.6
0.03856	0.04250	2.3	0.05785	0.05500	2.9
0.05785	0.04828	1.0	0.1157	0.08137	2.7
0.1157	0.05819	1.6			
0.2315	0.07364	1.7			

The dissociation constant of glycollic acid is 1.5×10^{-4} . The results are of the same order of magnitude. At low concentration the results are high but they decrease with the increase of concentration of the potassium salt and approach the required value.

The results with salicylic acid are similar although in general they are higher than those obtained with benzoic acid.

TABLE II

Dissociation constant of lactic acid.

- (i) With benzoic acid at 26°. K_1 of benzoic acid at 30° = 6.4×10^{-5} . $a = 0.02909$.
 (ii) With salicylic acid at 24°7'. K_1 of salicylic acid at 30° = 1.6×10^{-5} . $a = 0.01568$.

c .	b .	$K_2 = K_1.a.(c-b+a)/(b-a)^2$.	c .	b .	$K_2 = K_1.a.(c-b+a)/(b-a)^2$.
0.00438	0.03159	5.6×10^{-4}	0.02466	0.03363	5.2×10^{-4}
0.00548	0.03250	3.3	0.03288	0.03909	3.5
0.00822	0.03318	4.6	0.04932	0.04909	3.1
0.01233	0.03593	3.0	0.09865	0.07409	2.9
0.02466	0.04091	1.7	0.1973	0.1150	2.5
0.03288	0.04228	2.1			
0.04932	0.04681	1.8			
0.09865	0.05728	1.6			
0.1973	0.07046	1.7			

Dissociation constant of lactic acid is 1.4×10^{-4} . The values obtained with benzoic acid are of the same order of magnitude and approach it more nearly as the concentration is increased. The values are high at low concentrations but fall gradually as the concentration of the salt is increased.

The results obtained with salicylic acid are very similar although the values in general are of a higher order of magnitude than those obtained with benzoic acid.

TABLE III

Dissociation constant of n-butyric acid.(i) With benzoic acid at 25.9° . K_1 of benzoic acid at $30^{\circ} = 6.4 \times 10^{-5}$. $a = 0.02904$.(ii) With salicylic acid at 25.2° . K_1 of salicylic acid at $30^{\circ} = 1.6 \times 10^{-5}$. $a = 0.01608$.

<i>c.</i>	<i>b.</i>	$K_1 = K_1 \cdot a \cdot (c - b + a) / (b - a)^2$	<i>c.</i>	<i>b.</i>	$K_1 = K_1 \cdot a \cdot (c - b + a) / (b - a)^2$
0.00772	0.03544	6.0×10^{-5}	0.01688	0.03097	2.3×10^{-5}
0.01080	0.03872	2.2	0.03377	0.04677	8.4
0.01801	0.04527	1.0	0.04503	0.05689	6.5
0.03377	0.05729	1.3	0.06755	0.07727	4.3
0.04503	0.06494	1.3	0.1351	0.1379	2.3
0.06755	0.07923	1.3	0.2702	0.2478	1.8
0.1351	0.1161	1.2			
0.2702	0.1716	1.2			

The dissociation constant of butyric acid is about 1.5×10^{-5} . The values therefore approach this limit for higher concentrations. For low concentrations the values are high.

The salicylic acid is stronger than benzoic acid and as such given values are greater than those obtained by using benzoic acid. At low concentration the dissociation constant is high while it falls with increased concentration of potassium salt.